

Original Research Article

Assessment of Educational Environment in Islamic International Dental Hospital

Saadia Ejaz Bokhari, Ufaq Rao, Tariq Akbar, Zarish Khan, Abdul Haq, Yousuf Azimi

Abstract

Department of Periodontology, Islamic International Dental College Hospital, Islamabad

*Corresponding Author's Email:
drabdul.haq15@gmail.com

The objective of this study was to assess the educational environment of third year Bachelor of Dental Surgeon (BDS) students at Islamic International Dental College Hospital. The study was conducted using Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) inventory. DREEM questionnaire has worldwide validity. All 72 questionnaires were returned filled. Overall mean score found positive was 126.38 (maximum 200). Corresponding scores in subscales were 31.70 in students perception of learning, 28.83 in students perception of teachers, 20.61 in students academic self perception, 28.26 in students perception of atmosphere and 16.98 in students social self perception. Overall positive score with some areas requiring improvement in all subscales was found.

Keywords: DREEM, Educational environment, Perception

INTRODUCTION

When students enter any medical or dental institution, the climate or environment in which they have been studying and the way in which they have been taught till then suddenly changes (Khan et al., 2011; Roff, 2005; Mc Aler and Roff, 2001; Assessment of the educational environment in a newly established dental college, 2013; Roff and McAleer, 2001; Aneela et al., 2011). The environment therefore should be student friendly and student oriented focusing on the learning, understanding, logical reasoning and development of concepts and skills of the students (Gilani et al., 2016). The students are then evaluated by semester or annual examination.

Last few decades have seen a shift from teacher oriented to student oriented teaching techniques. Teaching involves learning, memorizing, understanding of knowledge and reasoning (Khan et al., 2011; Al-Ayed and Sheikh, 2008; Mc Aler and Roff, 2001; Assessment of the educational environment in a newly established dental college, 2013; Roff and McAleer, 2001).

In this article, therefore, perception of the educational environment of students is measured using Dundee

Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) criteria. The Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) was developed between 1994 and 1996(1). This criteria has been used all around the world in order to assess the educational environment of any particular institute at that particular point of time (Gilani et al., 2016; Al-Ayed and Sheikh, 2008; Roff, 2005; Aneela et al., 2011). There are 50 questions in these criteria which are divided into further 5 subscales:

1. Students perception of learning
2. Students perception of teachers
3. Students academic self perception
4. Students perception of atmosphere
5. Students social self perception

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Copies of original Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) were obtained in English language. Students of third year BDS, Islamic Interna-

tional Dental Hospital, were briefly explained the purpose of the study and they were told that their identities will be kept anonymous. 72 questionnaires were then distributed amongst the students. They were given 5 to 10 minutes to read and fill the questionnaires. All questionnaires were filled and returned. The questionnaires were then collected and data was analyzed using IBM SPSS statistics 23. Frequencies were then calculated for each item of each subscale. Also percentages of responses for each item of each subscale were calculated. Following is a guide to interpret the overall score:

0-50 Very Poor

51-100 Plenty of Problems

101-150 More Positive than Negative

151-200 Excellent

RESULTS

Total number of 72 students of 3rd year BDS from Islamic International Dental Hospital participated in this study out of which 9 were males (12.5%) and 63 were females (87.5%). The overall mean score from all 5 subscales of Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) was 126.38 out of 200. The general perception of students in all 5 subscales varied. (Table 1)

Student's Perception of Learning:

In 'Students' perception of Learning', there were 12 items used. The overall mean for this subscale was 30.91 and standard deviation was 7.12. The overall mean score of 12 items was 31.70 out of 48 showing positive perception of third year BDS students about learning. Responses showed that 54.2% agreed and 22.2% strongly agreed that they are encouraged to participate during teaching sessions, 47.2% agree and 9.7% strongly agree that they found the teaching stimulating. 33.3% agree and 8.3% strongly agree that the teaching is registrar centered. 48.6% agree and 12.5% strongly agree that teaching helps to develop their competence. 27.8% agree while 40.3% strongly agree that teaching is well focused. They feel they are being well prepared for their profession(34.7% agree ,27.8% strongly agree) and the time for teaching is put to good use (33.3% agree, 37.5% strongly agree). While they think that teaching excessively emphasizes factual learning(31.9% agree, 29.2% strongly agree) and they have clarity about the learning objectives of the course (48.6% agree,16.7% strongly agree).Some students agreed (40,3% agree,11.1% strongly agree) that they are encouraged to be active learners. Half of the students believe long term learning is emphasized over short term learning (41,7% agree, 8,3% strongly agree) while some think that teaching is too.

teacher centered (26.4% agree,6,9% (strongly agree). (Table 2)

Student's perception of teachers

In this subscale, there were 11 items used. .The overall mean for this subscale was 28.16 and standard deviation was 4.78.The overall mean score for all 11 items was 28.83 out of 44 which showed that teachers were teaching in the right direction but certain areas required improvement.

Responses of the students showed that 52.8% agreed and 23.6% strongly agree that course organizers are knowledgeable. 50% agreed while 6.9% strongly agreed that course organizers have patient centered approach to consulting. 20.8% agreed while only1.4% strongly agreed that course organizers ridicule the registrars. 38.9% agreed while 5.5% strongly agreed that course organizers are authoritarian. 33.3% agreed while 52.8% strongly agreed that course organizers have good communication skills with the patients.29.2% agreed while 25% strongly agreed course organizers provide good feedback to registrars. 34.7% agreed while 25% strongly agreed that course organizers provide constructive criticism. 58.3% agreed while 19.4% strongly agreed that course organizers give clear examples.19.4% agreed while 12.5% strongly agreed that organizers get angry during teaching sessions.55.6% agreed while 18.1% strongly agreed that course organizers are well prepared for their teaching sessions. 59.7% students agree while 12.5% students strongly agree that they are able to freely ask any questions. Table 3

Student's academic self perception

In this subscale, there were a total of 8 items present. The overall mean was 20.56 while standard deviation was 6.11. The overall mean score for 8 items was 20.61 out of 32 which showed students feel more on the positive side regarding academics.

Responses showed that 43.1% agreed while 9.7% strongly agreed that they are able to learn by the strategies which they used before. 37.5% agreed while 27.8% strongly agreed they were confident of their passing this year.30.6% agreed while 31.9% strongly agreed that teaching helps in developing their confidence. 26.4% agreed while 25% strongly agreed that last year work has been a good preparation for this year's work. 26.4% agreed and 22.2% strongly agreed that they were able to remember all they needed.34.7% agreed while 36.1% strongly agreed that about having learnt a lot about empathy in their profession.48.6% agreed while 5.6% strongly agreed that their problem solving skills are developing well. 54.2% agreed while 18.1% strongly agreed that much of what they are

Table 1. Frequencies:

Statistics		C1Score	C2Score	C3Score	C4Score	C5Score
N	Valid	72	72	72	72	72
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		30.9167	28.1667	20.5694	28.2917	16.8333
Std. Error of Mean		.84006	.56363	.72076	.76923	.43650
Std. Deviation		7.12810	4.78260	6.11585	6.52716	3.70382

Table 2. Students perception of learning

Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Encouragement to participate during teaching sessions	16(22.2%)	39(54.2%)	13(18.1%)	3(4.2%)	1(1.4%)
The teaching is often stimulating	7(9.7%)	34(47.2%)	21(29.2%)	7(9.7%)	3(4.2%)
The teaching is registrar centered	6(8.3%)	24(33.3%)	31(43.1%)	5(6.9%)	6(8.3%)
Teaching helps to develop my competence	9(12.5%)	35(48.6%)	18(25%)	7(9.7%)	3(4.2%)
The teaching is well focused	29(40.3%)	20(27.8%)	10(13.9%)	5(6.9%)	8(11.1%)
I believe I am being well prepared for my profession	20(27.8%)	25(34.7%)	19(26.4%)	1(1.4%)	7(9.7%)
Teaching time is put to good use	27(37.5%)	24(33.3%)	12(16.7%)	2(2.8%)	7(9.7%)
Teaching over emphasizes factual learning	21(29.2%)	23(31.9%)	22(30.6%)	2(2.8%)	4(5.6%)
I am clear about the learning objectives of the course	12(16.7%)	35(48.6%)	14(19.4%)	10(13.9%)	1(1.4%)
Teaching encourages me to be an active learner	8(11.1%)	29(40.3%)	21(29.2%)	8(11.1%)	6(8.3%)
Long term learning is stressed upon over short term learning	6(8.3%)	30(41.7%)	26(36.1%)	7(9.7%)	3(4.2%)
The teaching is extremely teacher centered	5(6.9%)	19(26.4%)	35(48.6%)	10(13.9%)	3(4.2%)

Table 3. Students perception of teachers

Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Course organizers are knowledgeable	17(23.6%)	38(52.8%)	14(19.4%)	2(2.8%)	1(1.4%)
Course organizers espouse a patient centered approach to consulting	5(6.9%)	36(50%)	20(27.8%)	8(11.1%)	3(4.2%)
The course organizers ridicule the registrars	1(1.4%)	15(20.8%)	26(36.1%)	20(27.8%)	10(13.9%)
The course organizers are authoritarian	4(5.6%)	28(38.9%)	30(41.7%)	5(6.9%)	5(6.9%)
Course organizers have good communication skills with patients	38(52.8%)	24(33.3%)	9(12.5%)	0(0%)	1(1.4%)
Course organizers are good at providing feedback to registrars	18(25%)	21(29.2%)	21(29.2%)	1(1.4%)	11(15.3%)
The course organizers provide constructive criticism here	18(25%)	25(34.7%)	18(25%)	5(6.9%)	6(8.3%)
Course organizers give clear examples	14(19.4%)	42(58.3%)	11(15.3%)	4(5.6%)	1(1.4%)
Course organizers get angry in teaching sessions	9(12.5%)	14(19.4%)	18(25%)	27(37.5%)	4(5.6%)
Course organizers are well prepared for their teaching sessions	13(18.1%)	40(55.6%)	13(18.1%)	4(5.6%)	2(2.8%)
I am able to ask the questions I want	9(12.5%)	43(59.7%)	12(16.7%)	6(8.3%)	2(2.8%)

Table 4. Students academic self perception

Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learning strategies which worked for me before still continue to work for me now	7(9.7%)	31(43.1%)	21(29.2%)	10(13.9%)	3(4.2%)
I am confident about my passing this year	20(27.8%)	27(37.5%)	21(29.2%)	1(1.4%)	3(4.2%)
Teaching helps to develop my confidence	23(31.9%)	22(30.6%)	15(20.8%)	6(8.3%)	6(8.3%)
Last years' work has been a good preparation for this years work	18(25%)	19(26.4%)	17(23.6%)	5(6.9%)	13(18.1%)
I am able to remember all I need	16(22.2%)	19(26.4%)	17(23.6%)	8(11.1%)	12(16.7%)
I have learnt a lot about empathy in my profession	26(36.1%)	25(34.7%)	13(18.1%)	3(4.2%)	5(6.9%)
My problem solving skills are developing well here	4(5.6%)	35(48.6%)	20(27.8%)	12(16.7%)	1(1.4%)
Most of what I have learnt seems relevant to a career in healthcare	13(18.1%)	39(54.2%)	12(16.7%)	5(6.9%)	3(4.2%)

Table 5. Students perception of atmosphere

Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The atmosphere is relaxed during consultation teaching	13(18.1%)	41(56.9%)	10(13.9%)	8(11.1%)	0(0%)
The course is well timetabled	8(11.1%)	32(44.4%)	11(15.3%)	10(13.9%)	11(15.3%)
Cheating is a problem on this course	4(5.6%)	16(22.2%)	28(38.9%)	17(23.6%)	7(9.7%)
There is relaxed atmosphere during lectures	26(36.1%)	29(40.3%)	7(9.7%)	4(5.6%)	6(8.3%)
I get opportunities to develop interpersonal skills	23(31.9%)	24(33.3%)	13(18.1%)	5(6.9%)	7(9.7%)
I feel at ease in teaching sessions socially	23(31.9%)	31(43.1%)	8(11.1%)	6(8.3%)	4(5.6%)
Atmosphere is relaxed during seminars/tutorials	26(36.1%)	30(41.7%)	11(15.3%)	2(2.8%)	3(4.2%)
I find this experience disappointing	8(11.1%)	13(18.1%)	21(29.2%)	7(9.7%)	23(31.9%)
I can concentrate well	20(27.8%)	19(26.4%)	16(22.2%)	7(9.7%)	10(13.9%)
Enjoyment outweighs stress of the course	3(4.2%)	13(18.1%)	24(33.3%)	17(23.6%)	15(20.8%)
Atmosphere motivates me as a learner	8(11.1%)	26(36.1%)	18(25%)	12(16.7%)	8(11.1%)
The registrars irritate the course organizers	1(1.4%)	16(22.2%)	38(52.8%)	10(13.9%)	7(9.7%)

Table 6. Students social self perception

Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
There is good support system for registrars who get stressed	1(1.4%)	23(31.9%)	29(40.3%)	11(15.3%)	8(11.1%)
I am extremely tired to enjoy the course	15(20.8%)	23(31.9%)	14(19.4%)	17(23.6%)	3(4.2%)
I rarely get bored on this course	5(6.9%)	22(30.6%)	16(22.2%)	18(25%)	11(15.3%)
My friends on this course are good	18(25%)	38(52.8%)	13(18.1%)	3(4.2%)	0(0%)
I have a good social life	31(43.1%)	21(29.2%)	10(13.9%)	3(4.2%)	7(9.7%)
I seldom feel lonely	15(20.8%)	18(25%)	20(27.8%)	3(4.2%)	16(22.2%)
My accommodation is pleasant	8(11.1%)	35(48.6%)	17(23.6%)	7(9.7%)	5(6.9%)

learning seems relevant to a career in healthcare. Table 4

Student's perception of atmosphere

In this subscale, 12 items were used. Overall mean for this subscale was 28.29 and standard deviation was 6.52. The overall mean score for 12 items was 28.26 out

of 48 which showed a positive perception of 3rd year BDS students about the atmosphere in which they are studying. The students' responses showed that the atmosphere is relaxed during consultation teaching (56.9% agree, 18.1% strongly agree). 44.4% agreed while 11.1% strongly agreed that course was well timetabled. Only 22.2% agreed while 5.6% strongly agreed that cheating was a problem. 40.3% agreed and 36.1% strongly agreed that there is a relaxed atmosphere

during lectures.33.3% agreed while 31.9% strongly agreed about having opportunities for them to develop interpersonal skills.43.1% agreed while 31.9% strongly agreed that they were comfortable socially in teaching sessions. 41.7% agreed while 36.1% strongly agreed that there is a relaxed atmosphere during seminars and tutorials.18.1% agreed while 11.1% strongly agreed that they found the experience disappointing. 26.4% agreed while 27.8% strongly agreed that they were able to concentrate well. Only 18.1% agreed while 4.2% strongly agreed that enjoyment outweighed the stress of the course. 36.1% agreed while 11.1% strongly agreed that atmosphere motivated them as a learner. Only 22.2% agreed while only 1.4% strongly agreed that registrars irritate the course organizers. Table 5

Student's social self perception

In this subscale, there are a total of 7 items. The overall mean for this subscale was 16.83 and standard deviation was 3.70. The overall mean score of these 7 items was 16.98 from 28 which showed that social self perception of students was not too bad.

The students' responses showed that 31.9% agreed and 1.4% strongly agreed about having a good support system for registrars who get stressed. 31.9% agreed and 20.8% strongly agreed that they are extremely tired to enjoy the course. 30.6% agreed and 6.9% strongly agreed that they were rarely bored on this course. 52.8% agreed while 25% strongly agreed that they have good friends on this course. 29.2% agreed while 43.1% strongly agreed that their social life is good. 25% agreed and 20.8% strongly agreed that they seldom feel lonely. 48.6% agreed while 11.1% strongly agreed that the accommodation is pleasant.

The overall score

Overall mean score was 126.38 from 200 showing the perception of 3rd year BDS students of their educational environment in Islamic International Dental Hospital was more positive than negative. In all 5 subscales, improvement can be done in certain areas.

DISCUSSION

Educational environment remains an important factor while determining the success of curriculum and performance of pupils. Therefore, this study was conducted on 3rd year BDS students of Islamic International Dental Hospital to see what the perspectives of students about their educational environment were.

In this study, perception of students was found to be more positive as compared to negative about their

educational environment but steps should be taken to improve all 5 areas. Overall mean score for all 5 subscales of DREEM came out to be 126.38 out of 200 (63.19%) in this study. Mean score in student's perception of learning was 31.7 out of 48 which shows a good perception of students about their learning but still improvement can be done. The mean score in student's perception of teachers is 28.83 from 44 which is more positive than negative but it can still be improved. While in a student's academic self perception, the mean score is 20.61 out of 32 which is again more positive than negative but requires improvement. Mean score in student's perception of atmosphere is 28.26 out of 48 which is more positive than negative but has room for improvement. While in students' social self perception, mean score is 16.98 out of 28 this is positive but requires improvement.

The results of this study are not much different from other studies. One study from private and government medical colleges from Pakistan had a mean score of 125 out of 200, which is almost the same to the score in this study (Khan et al., 2011). A study from Srilanka reported a mean DREEM score of 107.4 (Rajesh et al., 2005). A study from the UK reported a mean DREEM score of 139 (Roff and McAleer S. Harden, 1997; Dunne et al., 2006). In studies in Malaysia (Al-Naggar et al., 2014) and Nepal (Mc Aleer and Roff, 2001), the overall scores were found to be 125.3 and 130 respectively.

The limitation of this study is that the number of participants is not too high as it was only performed on 3rd year BDS students in Islamic International Dental Hospital therefore study is limited on finding out the perception of the education environment at Islamic International Dental Hospital to one batch of students only.

CONCLUSION

The environment was found to be good in all subscales but it can still be improved. Therefore necessary steps should be taken to improve all 5 areas.

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